

ENHANCING MENTAL HEALTH, REPRODUCTIVE AND SEXUAL HEALTH CARE FOR STUDENTS OF THAI NGUYEN UNIVERSITY OF AGRICULTURE AND FORESTRY THROUGH CLUB ACTIVITIES

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Abstract

The Student Club is a place with rich activities, suitable to the needs and interests of students, creating an environment for students with abilities and aptitudes to be revealed and developed. Besides the new value orientation, creating conditions for students to mature in all aspects. The Student Club was formed by the Students' Union to create conditions for students to communicate, behave, have healthy entertainment, express their views and aspirations, and support to solve difficult problems and problems in study, work, and in life; Enhancing mental health, reproductive and sexual health care for students of Thai Nguyen University of Agriculture and Forestry. The article is within the framework of the topic "Improving the capacity of mental health care, reproductive and sexual health care for students of Thai Nguyen University of Agriculture and Forestry", funded by the scientific research topic of 2022 students. Code: SV2022-34; Admisnistor: Ho Chi Minh Communist Youth Union -Thai Nguyen University of Agriculture and Forestry (TUAF).

Keywords: mental health care, reproductive and sexual health care, Student, TUAF, club.

1. Introduction:

In Vietnam, the youth age group from 15 to 24 years old has about 7.5 million people, of which about 1.7 million are students studying at 235 universities and colleges worldwide country (data does not include security and defense schools) [Report of the Ministry of Education and Training for the school year 2017-2018 Ministry of Health: First National Survey on Adolescents and Adolescents (SAVY) (2003) and Second (2008)]. The diverse socio-cultural contexts between regions along with strong changes in the economic, cultural, and social fields of Vietnam have led to changes in the concept of love, sex, and marriage. individuals, families... from many walks of life, especially young people. Recent studies have also shown that, in Vietnam, teenagers have an increasing rate of premarital sex and the level of premarital sex is increasing [According to the results of the Population Change and Family Planning Survey on April 1, 2017: Thai Nguyen province located in the Northern Midlands and Mountains, where the rate of abortion/abortion and menstrual regulation suction is high. was always higher than the rest of the country within 5 years (2012-2017)]. The age of the first sex is decreasing. According to the results of the 2019 Population and Housing Census of the General Statistics Office, underage childbearing still exists in Vietnam. On a national scale, underage women (from 10 to 17 years old) giving birth account for 3.3%; the highest in the Northern Midlands and Mountains (9.7‰). Over the years, Vietnam has made great efforts and achieved impressive results in population work with a record of reducing abortions. In 2016, the number of abortions stood at 265,536 compared to 470,000 in 2010. However, according to international reports, Vietnam is still one of the countries with the highest abortion rate in the world []. As a large university located in Thai Nguyen province, Thai Nguyen University of Agriculture and Forestry recruits 1,600-

1,700 students for 23 undergraduate majors, formal systems, and work-study programs, of which students from ethnic minorities are a large percentage.

In the context of the prolonged Coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic, negative impact on all aspects of society. For students, the transition from face-to-face to online learning makes the acquisition of knowledge difficult, and psychological health problems are also greatly affected. According to the survey "Students' mental health and health during the Covid-19 period" 37,150 students (17,969 female (48.4%) and 19,181 male (51.6%)) from October 18, 2021, to On October 25, 2021, Ho Chi Minh National University: 56.8% lacked concentration or had no interest in studying, showing that the teaching organization during the Covid-19 period was still limited. Many students are not satisfied with the quality of online lectures, and although their assessment of online learning pressure is not different from other groups, they are under higher pressure and are also the group that often faces problems. mental health than other groups (65.1%) [].

Therefore, improving the capacity of mental health care as well as reproductive and sexual health care is one of the important and necessary issues in the process of studying and working with students. Improving students' capacity and understanding, helping students overcome difficulties, and bringing high quality and efficiency to the process of studying and working. In addition, the activity also helps each individual to be more confident and active in learning as well as in life. This is a very necessary and useful job on the path of student development and career in the future. Strengthening mental health care, and sexual and reproductive health care for students through club activities is a type of organization, both a mode of operation and an important part of society. important role of the Student

Union organization at the University is to assist in solving complex and important problems in study and daily life, meeting the legitimate needs of students.

2. Overview of the research situation in the field of the topic

Health for everyone is a great goal, a strategic goal of the World Health Organization (WHO), of many developed countries and the health sector of our country, and also a common measure of all cultural societies. smart, clone. Physical health cannot be separated from social mental health and increasingly must affirm the important role of mental health in a common effort to improve the quality of life for everyone in a developed society. . From a legal perspective, according to Article 1, Youth Law (2020): "Youth are Vietnamese citizens from sixteen to thirty years old". The World Health Organization (WHO) mental health survey showed that on a sample of 1,202 Vietnamese primary and secondary school students aged 10-16 years old, the percentage of students with problems with overall mental health was 19.46%

[https://www.nami.org/Template.cfm?Section=federal_and_state_policy_legislation&template=/Content-Management/ContentDisplay.cfm&ContentID=43804]. Another study by Mai Huong Day Psychiatric Hospital with the University of Melbourne (Australia) within the framework of the project "Care for students' mental health" showed that there is always a proportion of students with mental health problems in schools. Regarding mental health, there are 15.94% of children with mental disorders in the total number of students at all levels.

Reproductive health and sexual health are important factors that determine the healthy physical and mental development of adolescents and young adults. . Investment in reproductive and sexual health care is an investment in the development of the nation and nation, contributing to improving the quality of human resources, contributing to the industrialization and modernization of the country. Right at the 1994 International Conference on Population and Development (ICPD), the heads of more than 190 participating countries pledged to implement the ICPD's Action Plan (ICPD PoA) which cares for women's reproductive and sexual health. Women and girls are always a priority along with education, professional development, job creation, and elimination of forms of unfair treatment of women, especially girls... At conferences evaluating the implementation of the United Nations PoA, the organization of a specific service delivery network (YFS), of good quality, and appropriate to the age group and culture of each country is mentioned, especially the comprehensive reproductive and sexual health education (CSE) including life skills and the participation of adolescents and young people in the entire process of policy formulation, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation. as prerequisites for the health and development of adolescents and young adults. In the Global Strategy on the Health of Women, Children and Adolescents 2016, to work towards the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals by 2030, the United Nations has also emphasized the care of reproductive health and reproductive health for children.

VTN, TN through increasing investment in health care, increasing universal coverage (UHC), promoting the leadership role of all levels of government, and participation of individuals and communities in care health. Although Vietnam has achieved certain successes in reproductive and sexual health care for adolescents and young adults, a series of guidelines, policies, and technical guidelines have been issued such as:

- The policy system on reproductive and sexual health for adolescents is relatively complete with documents that refer to aspects related to the reproductive and sexual health of adolescents and young men at different levels, demonstrating commitment government.

- Promulgating Guidelines for providing youth-friendly health services (According to Decision No. 4617/QĐ-BYT dated November 16, 2007, of the Ministry of Health).

- Promulgating national guidelines on reproductive health care services, including content on the reproductive health of pregnant women and young people (According to Decision No. 4620/QĐ-BYT dated November 25, 2009, and Decision No. 4128 /QĐ-BYT dated July 29, 2016, of the Ministry of Health).

- Include many indicators related to reproductive health into the set of statistical indicators on Vietnamese youth (according to Circular No. 11/2018/TT-BNV dated September 14, 2018, of the Ministry of Home Affairs).

- Decision No. 1679/QĐ-TTg dated November 22, 2019, of the Prime Minister approving the Vietnam Population Strategy to 2030;

- Decision No. 3781/QĐ-BYT dated August 28, 2020, of the Ministry of Health approving the National Action Plan on reproductive and sexual health care for adolescents and young adults in the period 2020 - 2025;

- Decision No. 5914/QĐ-BYT dated December 29, 2021, of the Ministry of Health on promulgating the Project on Reproductive and sexual health care for adolescents and young adults in the 2021-2025 period.

But there are still some inadequacies such as limited knowledge and skills on reproductive and sexual health care of adolescents and young adults; education on reproductive and sexual health has not been accessible on a large scale; The provision of information and friendly services on reproductive and sexual health have not yet met the diverse needs of adolescents and young adults. Status of early sex, unsafe sex, unwanted pregnancy, unsafe abortion, risk of sexually transmitted diseases... Especially, Thai Nguyen University of which the Thai Nguyen University of Agriculture and Forestry is a member of the project is not out of that situation. It is necessary and appropriate to strengthen the capacity of mental health care and reproductive and sexual health care for students of the University of Agriculture and Forestry through club activities.

3. Method and Some concepts

3.1. Method:

- * Document analysis method: This method is applied to look up, synthesize summary reports, and collect available documents related to the topic.

- * Observation method: The authors observe the learning and living activities of students at the Thai

Nguyen University of Agriculture and Forestry in the academic year 2021-2022.

* Method of interviewing: The topic is to interview students, staff of the Youth Union, and lecturers of the school.

* Method of polling by questionnaire: The project was designed using questionnaires on google docs to collect survey information, get opinions for analysis, and understand the difficulties of 240 1st year students at Thai Nguyen University of Agriculture and Forestry.

3.2. Concepts:

Mental health is considered an integral part of the definition of health (see WHO, 2001), where mental

health is not only the absence of mental disorder, but also a state of comfort, confidence in one's abilities, self-control, competence, and the ability to realize one's potential.

According to the World Health Organization: "Reproductive health is a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being in all respects concerning the reproductive system, reproductive function, and processes. the reproductive process throughout life stages"

4. Results and discussions

4.1. Current status of mental health care, reproductive and sexual health care of students at the University of Agriculture and Forestry

Table 1

Structure of students participating in the survey by faculty:

Characteristic		Amount N = 240	Rate %
Sex	Male	115	47.9
	Female	124	51.7
	Other	1	0.4
Faculty	Faculty of Biotechnology - Food Technology	36	15.0
	Faculty of Animal Husbandry and Veterinary Medicine	98	40.4
	Faculty of Environment	30	12.5
	Faculty of Agronomy	28	11.7
	Faculty of Economics and Rural Development	16	6.7
	Faculty of Forestry	19	7.9
	Faculty of Resource Management	14	5.8

Awareness of mental health: through a survey of 240 students, 45.1% of the respondents answered correctly what mental health is. When asked about mental health problems that students face, especially after 1 year of study in the context of Covid-19, 45.2% of students answered: They feel that they have many vague shortcomings about their purpose. live themselves often feel tired, anorexia; 36.5% of students answered: Feeling tired without energy is the main mental health problem students encounter.

"I don't often talk about my studies and my life to my parents, but I just call my parents to check on my family. When I talk about my studies to my parents, I am afraid of scolding because my study results are not very good. As for things in life and studying, I often share them with my friends and lovers" (Student major: Forest resource management, 1st-year student, Ethnic: Kinh).

"Due to the age difference, I usually don't like talking to adults like my parents and teachers, but I prefer talking to friends and lovers" (Student of major: Forestry, 1st-year student, Ethnic: Tày).

* Reproductive health awareness: The survey results showed that 78.4% of the total students answered this question correctly.

* Awareness of healthy sex: Survey of students' perception of healthy sex at Thai Nguyen University of Agriculture and Forestry (Here, healthy sex is when it ensures all elements of safety, health, and well-being, comfort on a personal and relationship level), shows that your understanding of the factors that ensure healthy sexual performance is quite good. Therefore, comprehensive sex education will help students have a healthy sex life, both physically and mentally, and improve their quality of life.

"I see sex before marriage as a very normal thing. The world is developing day by day, so are people. Switching sex as an act of satisfying the physiological needs of both" (Student majoring: Animal husbandry, 1st-year student, Ethnic: Kinh).

"In my opinion, having sex before marriage is a very normal thing, especially in today's modern society, because with today's growing social trend, meeting the needs of self has become more and more important and the need for sex is also necessary. Therefore, depending on the person's needs and sexual orientation, more or less, they will have choices to meet their own needs". (Student majoring: Animal husbandry, 1st-year student, Ethnicity: Kinh).

The club creates activities and playgrounds to help union members, youth, and students express their thoughts and comments on issues of mental health, reproductive health, and sexuality. Towards improving the capacity of students to take care of mental health, reproductive and sexual health during their studies and help them develop soft skills, confidently share difficulties...etc. Contributing to improving the morale as well as the quality of learning for students. Some activities carried out by the Club:

- Connecting and exchanging activities between schools: sports, arts: 1h30'-2h/session, Bringing exchange opportunities for students, relieving stress in the learning process.

- Organize seminars, pieces of training, seminars with lectures on some topics of mental health care, and reproductive health for students: from 1.5h-2h/session, for example: Be the leader self, Gender stereotypes and gender discrimination, Gender sensitivity, gender responsibility and stories from students. Prevention of sexual harassment and abuse, Youth with sexual and reproductive rights, Responding to gender-based

violence and sexual abuse, Contraceptive measures; The expression of gender and sexual prejudice in the mass media, in public space; Dating violence and how to avoid it; Safe sex, healthy sex, responsible sex...

- Introduction of books and materials: 2 hours/session on topics such as sexually transmitted diseases and HIV; LGBT+...

- Art exhibitions, and exchanges with speakers, and experts to strengthen connections with students inside and outside the Thai Nguyen University of Agriculture and Forestry.

4.2. Discussion

- It is necessary to have close coordination between the Youth Union, the Student Union in the school, and the club so that the school students can update their knowledge about mental health and reproductive health.

- Towards replicating the student health club model in the coming time for the whole of Thai Nguyen University.

- Enhance the effectiveness of direct communication for the target audience, which is university students, focusing on communication with the participation of peer groups. When carrying out health education communication, it is necessary to illustrate many documents and pictures suitable for young people and communicate indirectly by distributing communication materials such as leaflets, handbooks, and communication through Fanpage, Facebook, and Instagram...

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EDUCATION ON PREVENTING ETHNIC SECONDARY STUDENTS FROM CHILD MARRIAGE IN THE NORTHERN MOUNTAINOUS REGION OF VIETNAM

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Abstract

In this article, the author has mentioned the basic issues in education to prevent ethnic secondary students from child marriage, including objectives, contents, methods, and forms of education.

Keywords: child marriage, ethnic secondary student, education, mountainous region, marriage.

1. Introduction

Marriage means the establishment of a husband-and-wife relationship between a man and a woman in accordance with the law on marriage conditions and marriage registration. When performing a marriage, apart from the voluntary and mutual agreement between the man and the woman, one of the mandatory conditions that must be complied with is the marriage age as prescribed by law. According to the provisions of Clause 1, Article 8 of the Law on Marriage and Family (2014) of Vietnam, the marriage age for men is 20 years and more, and for women is 18 years and more [1]. This regulation is based on the study of socio-economic conditions in Vietnam in order to ensure the normal psycho-physiological development of young men and women, and it is important for them to be able to handle responsibilities in the role of a husband and a wife, a father and a mother when they step into a family

life. Compliance with regulations on the marriage age is necessary for sustainable family happiness.

In the Northern mountainous provinces of Vietnam, the phenomenon of child marriage is still existing and has been causing many serious consequences both physically and psychologically for young people, adversely affecting the quality of the race, hindering the quality of life and socio-economic development, social progress, and sustainable development of ethnic areas.

In this article, we have mentioned the basic issues in education to prevent ethnic secondary students from child marriage, including objectives, contents, methods, and forms of education.

2. Contents

2.1. Objectives of education to prevent secondary students from child marriage in the Northern mountainous region of Vietnam

- To raising awareness for students in terms of the risks and consequences of child marriage. The school